

Evaluation of Water Quality and the Availability and Distribution of Phytoplankton in Dukku River, Kebbi State, North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The current study was aimed at determining the physicochemical parameters affecting the availability of phytoplankton in Dukku River water, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. A total of twenty-four (24) water samples were collected from three sampling points (upper, mid, and downstream) weekly. The standard method of APHA (2010) was used for the analysis of physiochemical properties. Parameters measured include temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD), and phytoplankton availability. The results indicate that the highest temperature at both sites was recorded in April with a value of 33.0°C, and the lowest temperature was 23.7°C in January for the upper stream. The pH was neutral to slightly acidic throughout the sampling points, and it was within the range for inland waters (pH 6.5–8.5) as well as for culturing tropical fish species and domestic purposes. Twenty-four (24) species of phytoplankton were observed in this study, belonging to four classes: *Bacillariophyta*, *Chlorophyta*, *Cyanophyta*, and *Euglenophyta*. *Synedra japonicum* of the class *Bacillariophyta* was found to be the most diverse species (48.1%) at the upper site, followed by *Nostoc commnitum* of the class *Cyanophyta* with (28.3%) downstream and *Dinobryon bavaricum* of the class *Chlorophyta* with (22.5%) midstream. The State Ministries of Water Resources and Environment should set up appropriate monitoring and controlling units to regulate sewage discharged into the river and conduct further research on water quality as it affects phytoplankton, zooplankton, and fish availability and distribution.

Keywords: Distribution, Dukku, Evaluation, Kebbi, Phytoplankton, Water

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Water is dynamic medium and its quality depends on physical (colour, temperature, transparency, turbidity, and odour), chemical (pH, electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, fluoride, and nitrates etc), biological (phytoplankton and zooplankton) and bacteriological parameters [1]. Several environmental factors such as temperature, salinity, nutrients and light are considered to be the most important factors affecting the growth rate of fish [2]. Studies have shown that natural water possesses various physicochemical properties such as dissolved oxygen (DO), water temperature, pH and water depth. Water temperature is important in relation to fish life and all life processes are accelerated or slowed down by temperature

changes in the environment [1]. The temperature of running water usually varies seasonally and daily and among locations due to climate, elevation, and the extent of streamside vegetation and the relative importance of groundwater inputs [3]. The amount of dissolved oxygen in water depends on surface area, temperature etc. In natural water, colour is due to the presence of humic acids, fulvic acids, metallic ions, suspended matter, plankton, weeds and industrial effluents. Colour is removed to make water suitable for general and industrial applications and is determined by a visual comparison of the sample with distilled water [4]. Oxygen is one of the most important factors in any living ecosystem. Dissolved oxygen is an important factor in assessing water quality and monitoring

oxygen concentration helps to know the "health" of a water body [5].

Phytoplankton are microscopic plants containing chlorophyll, that float or swim on the upper surfaces of water or are suspended in the water column, where they are dependent on sunlight for photosynthesis [5]. In the process of photosynthesis, phytoplankton release molecular oxygen into the water as a waste by-product. It is estimated that about 50% of the world's oxygen is produced via phytoplankton photosynthesis while the rest is produced by plants [6]. Carbon dioxide is the main source of carbon for phytoplankton that in turn serves as food for zooplankton and fish [7]. Phytoplankton, being primary producers, hold a significant place in the aquatic food chain and all life forms including zooplankton are dependent on them [6].

Phytoplankton growth depends on the availability of carbon dioxide, sunlight, and nutrients. Phytoplankton, like land plants, require nutrients such as nitrate, phosphate, silicate, and calcium at various levels, depending on the species [8]. Some phytoplankton can fix nitrogen and can grow in areas where nitrate concentrations are low. They also require trace amounts of iron which limits phytoplankton growth in large areas of the ocean because iron concentrations are very low. Other factors influence phytoplankton growth rates, including water temperature, salinity, water depth, wind and predators [9].

When conditions are right, phytoplankton populations can grow explosively, a phenomenon known as a bloom. Blooms in the ocean may cover hundreds of square kilometers and are easily visible in satellite images. A bloom may last several weeks, but the life span of any individual phytoplankton is rarely more than a few days [4].

Phytoplankton analysis gives an overall idea of the environmental condition of the water body both at the time of growing and sampling. Although phytoplankton is present in water bodies, its supply as a food supplement can be increased through external supply from cultures or by the development of prevailing algae through fertilization [6].

Water is regarded as an essential nutrient for all forms of life. The survival and activity of organisms depend on the environmental and physicochemical characteristics of water. In aquatic systems, water rich in physicochemical and biological parameters is not suitable for human consumption and can have side effects on the survival and growth of fish [5]. The residual or side effects of physicochemical and biological indices

of water have prompted the need for corrective measures to maintain the water chemistry of the river [7]. This will help society become aware of the quality of the water used for daily consumption and also maximize plankton and fish production in the study area [8].

Phytoplankton is a food source for aquatic organisms and has been analysed to be a major source of the world's oxygen [4]. Due to its relative advantages in the aquatic environment, this study was designed to assess its availability in the study area. The results of the study are expected to provide information to fish farmers in the study area.

1.1 Aim of the study

The aim of the research is to study the physicochemical parameters affecting the availability and distribution of phytoplankton in Dukku River water, Birnin Kebbi.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the physicochemical characteristics of Dukku River water.
2. Assess the availability, diversity and distribution of phytoplankton species in the area.
3. To form a baseline for further research on water quality as it affects diversity and distribution of flora and fauna in Dukku River.

2.0 Material and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Kebbi State is located between latitudes 10.00°-13.00° N and longitudes 4.00°- 6.00°E (Figure 1). Dukku River is one of the most ancient rivers that exist under the Gwandu emirate and is the biggest and largest river in Kebbi State, covering an area of 457.92 km² [10]. It flows eastward to Yauri, where it joins the Kainji River in Niger State. The river is located in the north-west, along Makera village – Birnin Kebbi road to the left and Tarasa village – Birnin Kebbi road to the right, and within Birnin Kebbi metropolis. Dukku River plays significant roles in the history, culture and economic activities of the state. Most towns and villages in the state are situated near the river system. The river serves as a source of water for humans and animals, as well as for irrigation during the dry season and is the major source of raw water for the Kebbi State treatment plant [11].

The entire land area appears to lie on flat terrain except for intermittent rocks outcropping here and there and an undulating landscape that forms its

natural drainage system with Dukku's river as the major channel [12]. The climatic condition of Birnin Kebbi is synonymous with that which obtains in Kebbi and Sokoto regions. Rainfall occupied the period from mid-May to mid-September the wet season which is followed by the dry season from September to April [12].

Also, during the dry season, the short span temperature conditions of the cold period as well as the hot period occur, with the cold persisting from November to late February or early March. It is

characterised by colder nights and mornings, as well as dry dust-laden wind blowing from the direction of the Sahara desert. A dusty haze occasionally reduces visibility. This could occur both during the day and at night. Following the Harmattan (cold dry) season is the hot dry season. The area falls within a savannah zone, open (tsetse fly) free grassland that is suitable for the cultivation of grain crops and the rearing of livestock [12]. Birnin Kebbi has an impressive geographical area of 457.92 km².

Figure 1: Map showing the location of Birnin Kebbi

2.2 Sample Collection

Three sampling sites were selected and named stations A, B, and C (each was replicated three times) for the study. Station A was at the river axis, where a lot of human activities such as washing, bathing and fishing take place. Station B was at the mid-section of the reservoir, which represents the area of lentic water; it is the transition zone between the riverine and lentic sections of the river. Station C was at the head water of the reservoir, which represents the lotic section and inflow of the reservoir.

Surface water samples were collected in clean 750 ml evaplastic bottles, from the sampling stations, for a period of 8 months. Each sample collected was taken to the Science Laboratory of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, for determination of physicochemical parameters. Temperature,

transparency and depth were measured at the study area using a mercury glass thermometer (2cm under the surface of the water). The planktons were collected from three stations with a standard plankton net, which was fixed at the field into plastic bottles containing a 10% formalin solution and was kept for the identification of phytoplankton.

2.3 Identification and Determination of Phytoplankton Density

Direct microscopic cell counts using the drop count technique as outlined by [13] were used to determine the phytoplankton cell density (number of cells per ml). A drop of concentrate was placed on a glass slide and the total number of individuals in that drop was counted. Prior to these counts, the glass dropper used was calibrated to determine the number of drops that gave one millimeter. The

phytoplankton were identified by a phytoplankton identification key. The physical parameters were done in situ while the chemical parameters were done in the laboratory.

2.4 Determination of Physicochemical Parameters

Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater were used for all measurements of physicochemical parameters.

2.4.1 Temperature

Water temperature values were recorded from a mercury thermometer graduated in units of $^{\circ}\text{C}$ by immersing the thermometer slightly under the surface of the water (2cm) for 5 minutes until the mercury stood at one place. The temperature readings were recorded immediately as described by [14].

2.4.2 Transparency

Water transparency was measured using a Secchi disc of 25cm in diameter [15]. The disc was lowered into the water and the depth at which it became invisible was recorded. Then it gradually withdrawn from the water and the depth at which it became visible was noted. The transparency was the mean of these two readings and was obtained using the following formula: Transparency = $(P_1 + P_2) / 2$ where:

P_1 = depth at which the disc disappeared and

P_2 = depth at which the disc reappeared after withdrawal.

2.4.3 Depth

The depth of each station was determined using a mushroom string. In this method, the depth of each station was measured by dipping the string until it settled down; the measurement were then taken and recorded in metres [16].

2.4.5 Electrical Conductivity

This was assessed using the EBA/10 model conductivity metre by dipping the metre into the water sample and the reading was taken and expressed in $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ [17].

2.4.6 pH (Potential Hydrogen ion concentration)

The pH was determined with a Model pH electronic metre at 25°C after standardization with buffer solution at pH 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0. The electrode was dipped into water sample and reading was taken and recorded [18].

2.4.7 Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

For the estimation of dissolved oxygen (DO), water samples were carefully taken into 250 ml reagent bottles avoiding air bubbles. The samples collected were fixed separately using Winkler's method in the field itself. Manganous sulphate and alkaline potassium iodide reagents were added soon after the collection of water samples and the bottles were transported to the laboratory for further estimation. Later the DO was estimated in the laboratory by dissolving the precipitate with concentrated sulphuric acid and then titrating the samples against sodium thiosulphate (0.025N) solution using starch as an indicator and the result was expressed in mg/l [19].

2.4.8 Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)

One hundred milliliters (100ml) of water sample was measured and poured into a 250ml conical flask using a graduated cylinder, 1ml of magnesium sulphate (MnSO_4) solution and 1ml of alkali-iodide-azide solution were added and the mixture was shaken vigorously to form a white precipitate. The sample was poured into BOD bottles wrapped and covered with black cello tape and kept in a cupboard in the laboratory to prevent light from penetrating the water sample. The solution was allowed to incubate in the dark for 5 days at 20°C . After incubation, the sample was shaken and titrated with 0.23M sodium thiosulphate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) using the Winkler titration method until the colour changed to pale yellow. The titration value of dissolved oxygen in the sample was recorded and the calculation was carried out as follows: initial dissolved oxygen (DO) minus final dissolved oxygen (DO) measured. Therefore, the reduction in DO equals BOD in mg/L [20].

2.4.9 Sodium (Na^+) and Potassium (K^+)

Six volumetric flasks were labeled 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10ppm containing stock solution, 2mL of solution diluted with 100ppm of distilled water, and 4mL of standard solution continuously up to 10mL of standard solution. Then the highest standard was used to calibrate to 100 scales reading of the machine, then the reading was taken and multiplied by 0.1. Sodium and potassium were determined from the standard calibration occurred and expressed in mg/L [19].

2.4.10 Hardness of Water

Twenty milliliters (20ml) of water sample were pipetted into a conical flask, and 5ml of buffer solution was added, followed by 3 drops of Eriochrome black T indicator solution. This was

titrated with 0.01M of EDTA. The titrated value was recorded as described by [21].

2.4.11 Phosphate

Two milliliters (2 ml) of the water sample were poured into a 50 ml flask. Additionally, 2 ml of phosphorus extraction solution, 2M of ammonium molybdate, and 35 ml of distilled water were added. Furthermore, 1 ml of freshly diluted stannous chloride was introduced. Subsequently, the flask was shaken, and the color intensity was measured using a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 660 nm. The readings of the samples were then recorded [19].

2.4.12 Nitrite

Fifty millilitres (50 ml) of the water sample were poured into a kjeldahl flask. Exactly 0.3g of magnesium oxide and 0.4 g of divalent alloy was added. The flask was attached to a distillation machine. Boric acid indicator in a 50ml conical flask was placed under the condenser, and the samples were distilled to collect the distillate, which was then titrated with standard acid. The titre value was recorded from the burette [22].

2.4.13 Calcium

This element occurs in water naturally; sea water contains approximately 400 ppm, while fresh water generally contains 1-2 ppm. One of the main reasons for the abundance of calcium in water is its natural accordance with the earth's crust [23]. [19] also reported that calcium is an important determinant of water hardness and that it also functions as a pH stabiliser. Because of its buffering qualities, calcium also gives water a better taste. Calcium is naturally present in water; it may dissolve in rocks such as limestone, marble, calcite, dolomite, gypsum, fluorite, and apatite. Calcium is a determinant of water hardness because it can be found in water as Ca^{2+} ions; magnesium is the other hardness determinant [6].

Calcium is a dietary requirement for all organisms, apart from some insects and bacteria [23]. He also added that calcium carbonate is the building stone of the skeletons of aquatic organisms; calcium phosphate is required for bone in animals; and plants store about 1% of their dry mass. According to [24], apart from the hardness of the determinant calcium, it may also influence the toxicity of other compounds. He also added that water hardness influences aquatic organisms concerning metal toxicity; in softer water, membrane permeability on the gills is increased. Calcium also competes with other ions for binding spots in the gills;

consequently, hard water better protects fish from direct metal uptake [23].

2.4.14 Magnesium

This element is found naturally in seawater, which is about 1300 ppm. After sodium, which is the most commonly found cation in oceans, fresh water contains approximately 4 ppm of magnesium [25]. Magnesium and other earth metals are responsible for water harness; therefore, water containing a large amount of alkali earth ions is called soft water [6]. A large amount of minerals contain magnesium, for example, dolomite and magnesium carbonate. Magnesium is also a dietary requirement for all organisms; it is also the central atom of the chlorophyll molecule and is therefore a requirement for plant photosynthesis. [26] also reported that it is unusual to introduce legal limits for magnesium in drinking water because there is no scientific evidence of magnesium toxicity, but in other compounds, for example asbestos, magnesium may be harmful [27].

2.4.15 Chloride

Chloride determination was performed by titration with silver nitrate (AgNO_3) as the titrant. Standard NF ISO 9297 was based on the [28]. It uses a colorimetric determination of the equivalent point (with silver chromate). With the same titrant, it is possible to use a potentiometric determination of the equivalent point.

The silver nitrate reacts with the chloride ion according to:

This application uses a potentiometric titration with a combined silver/reference electrode, and the equivalence point is detected using the inflexion point mode.

The titration is performed in an acidic solution. The results are expressed in mg/L of chloride (Cl^- with a molar weight of 35.453 g/mol) [28].

The formula used in calculating chloride was given as:

$$\text{Cl} = 1000 \times 0.05\text{M} \times \text{titer value sampled} - \text{titer value blank} (0.5)$$

Volume of water used

2.4.16 Carbonate and Bicarbonate

To the solution from bicarbonate determination, 1 ml of phenolphthalein reagent (0.25% in 50% alcohol) was titrated with the sulphoric acid, standard 0.05 M. Correct for the quantity of AgNO_3 solution necessary to give in 50 ml of Cl^-

free water with a 1 ml K_2CrO_4 indicator, the shade obtained at the end of titration of the sample [6].

2.5 Plankton Sampling

Qualitative plankton samples were collected by towing a silk plankton net of 25 cm in diameter and 65 mesh/cm tied to a bottle of 50 mL capacity at the base. The net was then sunk just below the water surface for 5 minutes at each sampling station. The samples were immediately fixed into a labelled plastic bottle containing a logo solution for the preservation of phytoplankton and were taken to the laboratory, where it was allowed to settle, using the drop-count technique [13]. A drop of the concentrate was placed on a glass slide, and the total number of individuals in that drop was counted, after which the decantation method was carried out. Direct microscopic cell counts were achieved prior to these counts, the glass dropper was calibrated to determine the number of drops in one millilitre. Therefore, the total number of cells per drop was multiplied by the number of drops per millilitre to determine the total number of individuals or cells per mL [29]. The same

procedure was used for zooplankton, but the labelled samples were preserved with 4% formalin and kept for identification of phytoplankton and zooplankton species with the aid of a compound microscope.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

Significant differences in the means of the physicochemical parameters of the reservoir were determined using analysis of variance (ANOVA). Separation of significantly different means was done using the least significant difference (LSD).

3.0 Results

3.1 Physico-chemical parameters of Dukku River Water

The physicochemical properties of water samples from three different sites (upper, mid, and down streams) of Dukku River water from January to August 2018 are presented in Tables 3, 4, and 5, respectively. The results obtained from the analysis of quality in the Dukku River show that most of the physicochemical parameters were within the measured permissible limits of World Health Organisation [1] standards for drinking water.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of water samples at upper stream of Dukku River Water

Parameters	Values at sampling sites							
	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August
T (°C)	23.7	26.93	30.76	33.00	31.06	32.00	28.00	30.00
pH	7.60	7.43	7.33	5.10	6.03	5.500	6.88	5.30
DO (ml/L)	3.57	3.27	3.20	5.03	4.60	4.73	2.73	3.40
BOD (ml/L)	18.46	14.13	18.53	17.60	17.10	18.46	13.30	21.43
CO_3^{2-} (ml/L)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.09	0
HCO_3^- (ml/L)	1.08	0.53	1.10	0.47	0.5	0.7	1.4	0.63
Cl^- (ml/L)	1.03	0.57	1.00	0.63	0.83	0.73	0.53	0.67
Na^+ (ml/L)	0.68	0.5	0.55	0.48	0.54	0.44	0.44	0.67
K^+ (ml/L)	0.48	0.37	0.48	0.34	0.44	0.38	0.34	0.54
Ca^{2+} (ml/L)	1.13	1.33	1.43	0.7	0.73	0.63	1.4	1.00
Mg^{2+} (ml/L)	0.50	0.20	0.43	0.30	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.27
NO_3^- (ml/L)	1.19	1.30	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.10	0.97	1.30

DO=dissolved oxygen, BOD=biological oxygen demand

Table 2: Physicochemical properties of water samples at mid-stream of Dukku River water

Parameters	Values at sampling sites							
	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August
T (°C)	24.03	27.93	31.20	33.57	30.40	32.87	28.87	31.10
Ph	7.77	7.43	7.50	6.70	5.70	6.67	7.18	6.67
DO (ml/L)	4.03	3.57	3.50	4.63	4.20	4.50	3.20	3.33
BOD (ml/L)	20.69	15.17	16.03	17.67	19	18.33	15.7	19.3
CO ³⁻ (ml/L)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.19	0
HCO ³⁻ (ml/L)	0.97	1.10	1.03	0.63	0.70	0.73	1.10	0.90
Cl ⁻ (ml/L)	1.00	0.67	0.57	0.73	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.77
Na ⁺ (ml/L)	0.59	0.63	0.72	0.44	0.39	0.49	0.54	0.53
K ⁺ (ml/L)	0.43	0.34	0.49	0.44	0.48	0.38	0.44	0.42
Ca ²⁺ (ml/L)	1.77	1.40	1.37	0.63	1.27	1.00	1.50	0.83
Mg ²⁺ (ml/L)	0.49	0.30	0.23	0.20	0.40	0.30	0.13	0.47
NO ³⁻ (ml/L)	1.39	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.10	1.10	0.63	1.50

DO=dissolved oxygen, BOD=biological oxygen demand

Table 3: Physicochemical properties of water samples at downstream of Dukku River water

Parameters	Values at sampling sites							
	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August
T (°C)	24.03	27.46	31.56	33.63	30.30	32.73	28.43	31.33
Ph	7.80	7.47	7.43	6.03	6.10	6.80	7.03	6.93
DO (ml/L)	3.27	3.10	3.33	4.50	5.10	4.40	3.40	3.57
BOD (ml/L)	16.61	16.67	17.03	18.4	17.33	18.3	15.7	19.73
CO ³⁻ (ml/L)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.18	0
HCO ³⁻ (ml/L)	1.17	1.17	1.20	0.73	0.60	0.70	1.20	0.93
Cl ⁻ (ml/L)	1.03	0.73	1.03	0.47	0.6	0.77	0.5	0.77
Na ⁺ (ml/L)	0.74	0.63	0.59	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.57	0.7
K ⁺ (ml/L)	0.43	0.38	0.47	0.39	0.48	0.38	0.38	0.48
Ca ²⁺ (ml/L)	1.27	0.57	1.50	1.00	0.97	1.00	1.57	1.03
Mg ²⁺ (ml/L)	0.59	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.40	0.20	0.20	0.40
NO ³⁻ (ml/L)	1.39	1.27	1.27	1.00	1.07	1.10	0.90	1.53

Variations of the parameters, Cl⁻, DO, BOD, Na⁺, K⁺, and Ca, were random and varied with months and regions. Seasonal changes influenced the temperatures of the three sites in a similar pattern: lowest in winter, greatest in spring, and moderate in summer. Consequently, levels of pH, CO₃⁻, HCO₃⁻, NO₃⁻, and Mg²⁺ were dependent, monthly and regionally, on the seasonal changes in environmental temperature. The tables below show the obtained results of each parameter with respect to the months and regions concerned in

the study. The table below shows the means of the physicochemical parameters.

3.2 Phytoplankton Species Identified in Dukku River

Overall phytoplankton (cell/ml) identified were up to 169 individuals of eighteen species and genera from four different families: *Bacillariophyceae* (7 genera), *Chlorophyceae* (5 genera), *Cyanophyceae* (5 genera), and *Euglenophyceae* (1 genus). The phytoplankton identified is presented in Table 4.

Phytoplankton monthly distribution percentage frequencies varied between the sites. Upper-stream has the highest phytoplankton availability in February > in August > in January > in July > in May, while insignificant in April and June having the same percentage. Midstream was greatly richest in phytoplankton in May > in March > in July > in June > in April > in January > in August while lowest in February. Down-stream obtained maximum phytoplankton availability in April > in June > in January > in March and July having the same percentage > in February > in August while lowest in May.

Shannon index (Table 5) was highest in upper-stream during the month of January, followed by February and then August. While the rest of the months were negligible. In mid-stream, it was highest in January, followed by May, followed by

March, followed by July, followed by April, followed by June, and then negligible in August. The Shannon index in the downstream was highest in June, followed by April, followed by March, followed by January, followed by February and July having the same value, and then negligible in the rest of the month.

Evenness was highest in upper-stream during the month of January, followed by August, followed by February, while in the rest of the months it was negligible. In mid-stream, it was highest in January, followed by February, followed by March and May having the same value, followed by June and April, and in August it was negligible. In the downstream, it was highest in February and July with the same value, followed by June, followed by April, followed by March, followed by January, and negligible in May and August.

Table 4: Phytoplanktons species identified in Dukku River

Sampling sites	Species	Frequency
Upper Site	<i>Westella botryoides</i>	11.10%
	<i>Eunotia flexuosa</i>	3.70%
	<i>Synedra ulna</i>	22.20%
	<i>Synedra japonicum</i>	48.10%
	<i>Euglina viridis</i>	14.80%
Mid Site	<i>Pediastrum boryanum</i>	2.20%
	<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aque</i>	14.60%
	<i>Synnedra ulna</i>	22.50%
	<i>Dinobryon bavaricum</i>	22.50%
	<i>Chaetophora attenuate</i>	17.90%
	<i>Tetrastum komarekii</i>	2.20%
	<i>Westella botryoides</i>	4.50%
	<i>Nitella brittlewort</i>	1.10%
	<i>Tabellaria fenestrata</i>	1.10%
<i>Oscillatoria aghardhii</i>	11.20%	
Down Site	<i>Pediastrum duplex</i>	1.90%
	<i>Nostoc commnitum</i>	28.30%
	<i>Westella botryoides</i>	15.10%
	<i>Eunotia flexuosa</i>	1.90%
	<i>Tetrastum komareki</i>	3.80%
	<i>Crucigenia crucifera</i>	24.50%
	<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i>	16.90%
	<i>Anabena aequalis</i>	1.90%
<i>Sarcina ventriculi</i>	5.70%	

Table 5: Monthly Shannon Index Values and Evenness of the Study Sites

Station		Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	June	July	Aug.	Mean
Upper-stream	Shannon	1.08	0.91	0	0	0	0	0	0.64	0.32
	Evenness	0.98	0.82	0	0	0	0	0	0.93	0.34
Midstream	Shannon	3.02	0.7	0.94	0.74	1.18	0.55	0.8	0	0.90
	Evenness	4.38	1.01	0.85	0.67	0.85	0.8	0.58	0	1.1
Down-stream	Shannon	0.68	0.64	0.91	0.94	0	1.01	0.64	0	0.49
	Evenness	0.62	0.93	0.83	0.86	0	0.92	0.93	0	0.63

4.0 Discussion

4.1 Physico-chemical Parameters

Temperature values vary significantly and range from 24 to 33°C, as shown in Table 1. A high temperature recorded that was above the WHO limit might be a result of the higher light intensity the water received from the sun due to global warming. The pH was neutral to slightly acidic throughout the sampling points, and it was within the range for the inland waters (pH 6.5–8.5) as well as for culturing tropical fish species as reported by [30] and for domestic purposes [1]. This can be a result of increased water levels during the rainy season. The DO and BOD range from 2.7–5.0 mg/L and 1.0–1.3 mg/L; 3.2–4.6 mg/g and 0.6–1.5 mg/g; 3.1–5.1 mg/L and 0.9–1.5 mg/L, as shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3. [30] reported that the DO concentration in unpolluted water normally ranges between 8 and 10 mg/L, and anything below 5 mg/L adversely affects aquatic life. The DO for drinking water is 6 mg/L, whereas 4–5 mg/L is the suitable range for fish and aquatic organisms, as against the work of [32], who recorded values of DO higher than 6 mg/l. The BOD highest value (1.5 mg/L) in both midstream and downstream streams was relatively low compared with the WHO standard of 7.0 mg/L. High BOD levels cause dissolved oxygen depletion, which could be detrimental to aquatic life.

The total hardness is the total soluble magnesium and calcium salts present in the water, expressed as CaCO₃. In most natural water, the predominant ions are those of bicarbonates associated mainly with calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium [14]. The concentrations of nutrients, such as nitrite and chloride, in the water samples were also determined. The nitrite level of the water samples at both sites was found to be above the permissible limits of 0.1 mg/L. The high level of nitrate may be a result of extensive farming taking place at the bank of the river, with the possibility of the farmers making use of fertilizers. The highest concentration of nitrate, as shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3, could be responsible for the

high population of phytoplankton in the Dukku River. This is in line with the findings of [33], which [32] cited and stated that an increase in nutrients causes phytoplankton multiplication.

4.2 Availability of Phytoplankton in Dukku River water

A total of twenty-four (24) species of phytoplankton were observed in this study, belonging to four classes: *Bacillariophyta*, *Chlorophyta*, *Cyanophyta*, and *Euglenophyta*. The most varied species were found in the upper site, with 48.1% *Synedra japonicum* of the class *Bacillariophyta*. These were followed by *Nostoc commnitum* of the class *Cyanophyta* with 28.3% in the downstream and 22.5% *Dinobryon bavaricum* of the class *Chlorophyta* in the midstream (17.7%), as shown in Table 4. According to [35], nutrient levels and probably temperature may have played a significant role in phytoplankton multiplication.

Nitrogen is a major constituent of several important plant substances. For example, nitrogen compounds comprise 40% to 50% of the dry matter of protoplasm, and they are constituents of amino acids, the building blocks of proteins [35]. Magnesium is important to limnologists because of its role as an essential nutrient in aquatic plant growth and development, especially as it relates to its function in chlorophyll molecules [36]. Calcium can leach from rocks but is more prevalent in waters from regions with deposits of limestone, dolomite, and gypsum. The pH of water affects the normal physiological functions of aquatic organisms, including the exchange of ions with the water and respiration. Such important physiological processes operate normally in aquatic biota under a relatively wide pH range (e.g., 6–9 pH units). There is no definitive pH range within which all aquatic freshwater life is unharmed or outside of which adverse impacts occur. Rather, there is a gradual “deterioration” in acceptability as the pH value becomes further removed from the normal range [36, 37, 38]. Calcium is important to aquatic

productivity, especially during the formation of shells, scales, and bones [39]. The potassium ion (K⁺) is highly mobile and can aid in balancing the anion (negative) charges within the plant. Potassium serves as an activator of enzymes used in photosynthesis and respiration [40].

Based on the pattern of the relative abundances of phytoplankton in the upper, mid-stream, and downstream streams, it was found that the different species can adapt in ways that cause phytoplankton relative abundances to vary within the same site and between sites and months. Hence, species nutritional requirements, life history, and fitness in environmental conditions varied. Phytoplankton composition changes with nutrient fluxes because individual taxa have different requirements [41].

5.0 CONCLUSION

The results obtained revealed varying levels of physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton in the Dukku River. However, all the parameters evaluated except temperature were within the standard limits set by the [1] for water for domestic use. Nitrate, chloride, phosphate, and other nutrients increase the density of phytoplankton in the study area. With an increasing density of phytoplankton, there will be an increasing density of zooplankton as they will have adequate food (plankton) to feed on. In turn, there is a tendency to increase the fish population in the area as they also have an adequate food supply (the zooplankton).

6.0 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made;

1. The water quality of the Dukku River is declining as a result of increasing discharges of sewage and human activities. The State Ministries of Water Resources and Environment should set up appropriate monitoring and control units to regulate sewage discharged into the river.
2. Enlightenment should also be done to stop intensive fishing activities, which may reduce the diversity of fish species.
3. Further studies should be conducted on other physicochemical parameters and heavy metals likely to be present in the river.

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

This article confirms that there are no conflicts of interest. The author has no financial or personal connections that could influence the neutrality of the information. Transparency is preserved to ensure the integrity of the information provided.

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